

SHEAR BEHAVIOR CURAUÁ FIBER REINFORCED POLYMER CONNECTORS FOR CONCRETE SANDWICH PANELS

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the mechanical performance of FRP shear connectors for sandwich panel construction. A shear grid connector, composed of curauá fiber-reinforced polyester resin, was fabricated and subjected to push-out tests to determine its load-carrying capacity, displacement, and stiffness. The results were compared with previous synthetic and natural FRP connectors. The curauá fiber connectors exhibited inferior mechanical performance compared to synthetic counterparts. However, grid connectors proved to be effective for shear connection in sandwich panels. This study contributes to the understanding of FRP connectors and provides insights for improving their design and application in sandwich panel construction.

KEYWORDS

Fiber-reinforced polymer; shear connectors; sandwich panels; curauá fiber; mechanical performance.

INTRODUCTION

Sandwich panels consist of two layers of concrete and an inner core of insulating material, interconnected by shear grid connectors. This system can be used solely for sealing purposes or with a structural function by transferring forces, while also providing thermal and acoustic insulation for the building (PCI, 2011). Shear grid connectors are used in the production of sandwich panels to bond the concrete layers and maintain the insulation foam in the correct position, while transferring the longitudinal shear resulting from panel bending from one layer to another, capable of resisting in one or two directions (Einea et al., 1991).

These connectors can be manufactured with various materials and different geometries, such as "C," "Z," and "M" shapes, metal bushings, hooks, metal grids, nails or plastic pins, and carbon fiber meshes (Azevedo, 2013). However, Lee and Pessiki (2006) point out that the use of metal connectors, especially in facade panels, creates thermal bridges that can result in increased energy consumption for the building and moisture-related problems.

Thus, there is a need to explore new solutions and materials capable of overcoming the energy efficiency loss resulting from the use of metal connectors. For this purpose, connectors made of glass fiber reinforced polymer (GFRP) bars in the form of continuous bars or trusses have been proposed (Einea et al., 1994). Several other FRP connectors have been subsequently proposed (Salmon et al., 1997; Hassan & Rizkalla, 2010; Naito et al., 2011; Tomlinson, Teixeira, & Fam, 2016). Among the FRP connectors, there are PerfoFRP type connectors, studied by Lameiras et al. (2013) and Silva (2020).

Lameiras et al. (2013) evaluated the use of fiberglass-reinforced polyester resin connectors for sandwich panels made of steel fiber reinforced self-compacting concrete. The connectors, produced by vacuum infusion, consisted of three models of plates with holes at their ends for anchoring the concrete layers, as well as an adhesively bonded model. The behavior of the connections was tested through pull-out tests and showed that the hole connectors are more attractive because, in addition to achieving a higher load capacity, they have a simpler manufacturing process and lower material consumption.

The PerfoFRP connectors studied by Silva (2020) also consisted of hole plates manufactured with fiberglass-reinforced polyester resin using the vacuum infusion system. Hole diameters ranging from 6.35 mm to 31.75 mm, with different spacings, were analyzed. Push-out tests showed that connectors with 12.70 mm holes exhibited the best performance, achieving higher strength. Connectors with smaller diameters (6.35 mm and 12.70 mm) experienced strength increases ranging from 4% to 45%, while larger holes (19.05 mm, 25.40 mm, and 31.75 mm) ranged from -6% to 25% strength gains.

Fiberglass is the most commonly used material in composite manufacturing due to its low cost, high strength, good durability, and thermal insulation properties (Agarwal et al., 2017). However, other synthetic fibers can be employed, such as carbon fiber, as used by Hassan and Rizkalla (2010) in a study providing design guidelines for precast concrete panels with carbon fiber-reinforced polymer (CFRP) shear grid connectors. The researchers used an analytical approach to determine whether the panel behavior was fully or partially composite, depending on whether the panel's insulation layer was XPS or EPS. Based on test results, they estimated the shear flow capacity of the CFRP grid connectors. The data showed a composite action of up to 85% for XPS insulation, with a nominal shear flow of 35 kN/m for the CFRP grid. The EPS insulation layer exhibited a composite action of 93%, representing a nominal shear flow of 70 kN/m for the CFRP grid.

Although synthetic fiber-reinforced polymer materials offer good strength and low weight compared to other construction materials, their application is expected to decrease. This is primarily due to high production costs, significant energy requirements, and high pollution levels associated with the manufacturing and recycling of these materials (Girisha et al., 2012).

For these reasons, natural fibers have been considered a viable alternative to replace synthetic fibers. Despite having lower mechanical properties, such as tensile strength and modulus of elasticity, compared to synthetic fibers, natural fibers exhibit values that are sufficiently high for various engineering applications (Salgado & Silva, 2021).

One of the suggested fibers for producing environmentally friendly polymer composites is curauá fiber, derived from the Amazonian bromeliad species *Ananas erectifolius*. Studies conducted with curauá fiber-reinforced polymers have shown that composites with a fiber concentration above 10% exhibit high toughness, attributed to the incomplete fracture of the sample due to the flexibility of the fibers (Monteiro et al., 2013). It was also observed that an increase in the fiber content directly influences the mechanical behavior of the composite, as a sample with pure epoxy obtained lower strength compared to the composite reinforced with 30% curauá fiber (Maciel et al., 2018).

This study proposes a new type of shear connector for concrete sandwich panels, in a grid format, that is produced with fiber-reinforced polymer (FRP) materials reinforced with curauá fibers. The main objective of the presented study is to develop a curauá fiber-reinforced polymer grid connector, determine the mechanical properties of the connection between the proposed connector and concrete through push-out testing, and compare the results of the connections evaluated experimentally in this work with the performance of PerfoFRP type connections.

METHODOLOGY

This section presents the methodological procedures of this study.

Proposal of curauá fiber-reinforced grid shear connectors

The proposed curauá fiber-reinforced grid connector consists of vertical and horizontal strips arranged to form a grid. It is a format inspired by previous research on grid connectors, such as Frankl et al. (2008), who used orthogonally oriented carbon fiber polymer strips, and Kim and You (2015), who used fiberglass coated with epoxy resin. In this case, since it involves a fiber of plant origin, the proposed geometry has more robust dimensions, measuring 15cm in width, 25cm in height, and 0.40cm in thickness, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Proposed grid connectors (all units in cm)

Regarding the application, the intention is to use the grid connectors as discrete connections, similar to the approach used by Lameiras et al. (2021). The authors tested a full-scale sandwich panel wall and used shear connectors consisting of perforated polymer plates. The connectors had lengths of 40cm and 60cm and were evenly distributed along the panel, positioned with their length parallel to the wall height.

Production of the connectors

The grid connectors were produced using a polymer composite made of orthophthalic polyester resin and curauá fiber. Since curauá fiber is of plant origin, the first step was to treat the fiber to remove impurities and ensure a good bond with the matrix. An alkaline treatment was performed following the work of Beltrami et al. (2014), which involved immersing the fibers in a solution of sodium hydroxide (NaOH) and distilled water at a concentration of 5% (w/v) for 2 hours at a temperature of 50°C. The fibers were then rinsed with tap water until reaching a neutral pH (pH = 7), dried at room temperature for 24 hours, combed, and cut to the desired length.

A portion of the treated fibers was used to produce test specimens for composite characterization through direct tensile testing. Using the vacuum infusion process and two layers of 35g curauá fiber aligned unidirectionally with polyester resin, a composite plate with dimensions of 25cm × 40cm (height × width) was produced. At the end of the vacuum infusion process, the final thickness of the composite was measured to be 0.1cm, and the composites had a fiber areal weight of 0.070g/cm², achieving a volumetric fiber fraction of 36% and a matrix fraction of 64%. The composite plate was divided and cut along its width into small sections measuring 1.5cm, in order to obtain specimens with dimensions of 25cm × 1.5cm × 0.1cm for tensile testing (see Figure 2).

a) Test setup

b) Specimens

Figure 1: Tensile test on the composite material

The tensile tests were performed using an MTS LandMark machine with a 5kN load cell. The tests were conducted under displacement control at a speed of 2mm/min, following the recommendations of

standard D3039 (ASTM, 2000). In total, 5 specimens were tested in the longitudinal direction, aligned with the fibers. The average ultimate strength obtained was 144.59MPa, and the elastic modulus was 16.50GPa.

Next, the grid connectors were fabricated using the vacuum infusion process and orthophthalic polyester resin. It was decided to use 5 layers of 35g curauá fiber aligned in order to achieve a thickness of approximately 4mm. The fibers were cut to a length of 25cm, weighed, and arranged in a grid pattern as shown in Figure 3a, with a spacing of approximately 2.5cm between the strips. After the vacuum infusion process (Figure 3b) was completed, the connectors were left to cure for 24 hours before being demolded and cut into the required shape and dimensions for application in the concrete block. The final aspect of a grid connector is shown in Figure 3c.

Figure 3: Manufacturing of the grid shear connector with curauá fiber

Description of specimens for push-out test

The specimens for the push-out test were manufactured following the geometry described in Silva (2020), with dimensions of 30cm (height) × 40cm (width) × 30cm (thickness), as shown in Figure 4. These specimens consist of reinforced concrete blocks with an EPS insulation layer, representing a precast sandwich panel wall.

Figure 4: Design of concrete block (all units in cm)

The shear connectors in the model have dimensions of 15cm (width) × 25cm (height) and were centrally positioned within the concrete blocks (see Figure 4b). This configuration ensured a cover of 2.5cm in all directions for the connectors and also allowed the spacing between the strips to be used as anchorage points to the concrete.

Production of concrete blocks

Figure 5 illustrates the process of manufacturing the concrete blocks. The production was carried out following the following steps: fabrication of wooden molds, assembly and installation of reinforcement, cutting of EPS, attachment of the connector to the EPS, installation of the EPS-connector assembly into the molds, and pouring of the concrete into the blocks.

a) Installation of the construction elements b) Concrete pouring of the block c) Concrete block

Figure 5: Manufacturing process of the concrete test specimens

The concrete used consisted of self-compacting concrete, produced with 852.5kg/m^3 of gravel, 633.3kg/m^3 of sand, 498.5kg/m^3 of Portland cement, 133.50kg/m^3 of limestone filler, 231kg/m^3 of water, and 9.20kg/m^3 of MasterGlenium 51 superplasticizer, as described by Cardoso (2020). The concrete was mixed using a mechanical mixer and had an average spread of 55cm. The compressive strength tests of the concrete were performed on cylindrical specimens with a diameter of 10cm and a height of 20cm. The tests were conducted on the same day as the push-out test, at an age of 17 days, resulting in an average compressive strength of 38.32MPa.

To reinforce the concrete layers, vertical steel bars with a diameter of 10mm and horizontal steel bars with a diameter of 8mm were used (see Figure 4). The insulation layer was made of EPS blocks measuring $30\text{cm} \times 30\text{cm} \times 5\text{cm}$ to fit the configuration of the wooden molds. Additionally, a 25cm height cut was made in the center of the EPS to accommodate the connector installation.

Push-out tests

To evaluate the shear behavior of the connections between the concrete and the proposed connectors in this study, tests were prepared according to the configuration shown in Figure 6. The tests were performed on 3 specimens and basically involved supporting the outer layers of concrete on metal plates and applying a load to the inner layer of concrete, causing downward displacement that induces shear in the connectors.

Figure 6: Setup for conducting the push-out test

The tests were performed on an EMIC DL universal testing machine with displacement control. The tests were conducted at speeds of 0.1mm/min up to 4mm of relative displacement between the outer and inner layers, and 0.5mm/min from 4mm to 30mm of relative displacement. This speed was maintained until the connectors failed, which was indicated by a drop in the load reading.

The average relative displacements between the outer layers and the inner layer of concrete were obtained using two Linear Variable Differential Transducer (LVDT) displacement transducers. These transducers were positioned on the inner layer of concrete, as shown in Figure 7, on both sides of the specimen. The average displacements were determined by averaging the displacement readings for a given load. The loads were measured using an HBM load cell with a capacity of 500kN. The data from these instruments were recorded using the HBM Spider 8 data acquisition module at a frequency of 1Hz. At the end of the tests, the connectors were extracted from the concrete blocks for analysis of cracks and failure modes.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 7 show the appearance of the grid connectors after being extracted from the concrete blocks following the push-out test to evaluate the failure modes. The connectors are shown in the same orientation as they were positioned within the block, with the outer part representing the supported concrete layer and the middle part representing the inner concrete layer.

It can be observed that the connectors were significantly compromised, with some experiencing complete failure. The failures and most of the damage occurred primarily due to the tensile forces acting on the connector strips during the tests. However, there are also signs of damage and deformations in the strips subjected to compression

Figure 7: Grid connectors extracted from the concrete blocks after push-out tests

In general, the connectors exhibited a consistent failure pattern. It is noteworthy that the most significant damage is concentrated in the region of the connector that was in contact with the EPS. This area shows a clearly different surface compared to the region embedded in the concrete, and it is where most of the ruptures, permanent deformations, and fiber detachment occurred. These factors can be attributed to the elastic properties of the composite material, which was able to accommodate the displacement of the inner concrete layer and the deformability of the EPS during the application of load until failure. Similar behavior was observed in the PerfoFRP connectors studied by Silva (2020), who reported a predominance of cracks in the contact region between the connector and the insulation layer.

During the push-out tests, superficial cracks aligned with the connector positions appeared on the upper part of the concrete blocks. However, there was no detachment of the connection from the concrete layer internally. This, combined with the smoother appearance of this region, indicates that the composite material exhibited good adhesion to the concrete layer, as there were no visible surface damages or noticeable movements.

An important point to highlight is the presence of loose fibers in the connectors of concrete block P02 (Figure 7b). This indicates that the layer of polyester resin surrounding the fibers was very thin and easily worn during the test, causing the strength of the connection to mainly rely on the curauá fibers. The lower amount of resin possibly explains why block P02 exhibited higher strength compared to the others, as the fiber is the strongest element of the composite.

Figure 8 presents the concrete specimen after the push-out test. All blocks exhibited similar maximum displacements, but there was variation in the load capacity of CP01 and CP03 compared to CP02, which withstood approximately double the load. Since all blocks were produced in the same manner with the same materials, this variation in load capacity can be attributed to minor inconsistencies that may have occurred during the fabrication of the connectors.

Figure 8: Push-out specimen after test

It is evident that there were significant vertical displacements of the inner concrete layer, a characteristic observed in all tested blocks, confirming the occurrence of shear in the connections. Overall, despite the large displacements, there was no fragmentation of the concrete layers, only localized displacements of the EPS layer.

The load capacity of the network-type connector was determined by dividing the maximum load from the push-out test by two, considering that, due to the symmetry of the test setup and specimen, each connector in the concrete block supported half of the load. The stiffnesses of the connections were also calculated by dividing their load by the displacement corresponding to the peak load. The results are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Push-out test results

Specimen	Load		Displacement		Stiffness	
	kN	COV	mm	COV	kN/mm	COV
Grid 01	7,93	0,39	12,44	0,09	0,64	0,30
Grid 02	14,18		13,33		1,06	
Grid 03	7,34		11,09		0,66	
Average	9,81	-	12,29	-	0,79	-

It was found that the grid connector made of polyester resin reinforced with curauá fiber achieved load, displacement, and stiffness values that differ from those found in the literature for a similar application. For example, Silva (2020) worked with PerfoFRP connectors reinforced with fiberglass for sandwich panels and obtained average displacement corresponding to a maximum load of 32.23kN, and stiffness values equal to 1.28mm and 26.38kN/mm, respectively.

Similarly, for the same application, the PerfoFRP connectors tested by Araújo (2023), reinforced with curauá fiber, reached a displacement corresponding to the peak equal to 5.16mm and a stiffness of 5.54kN/mm, for a load of 22.50kN. These compared results indicate that, considering only the load capacity, the grid connectors analyzed in this research would not be efficient as connections for sandwich panels, as they achieved considerably lower load values compared to those found in the literature for the same application.

However, to make a more meaningful comparison, it is necessary to subject the connection to design conditions. For example, we can determine the required quantity of shear grid connectors to support the total load of a sandwich panel. Assuming that the panel in question is 8 meters long, 3 meters high, with concrete layers 5cm thick, and is suspended by one of these layers while the other is supported by the connectors.

In this case, the first step is to determine the characteristic value for the resistance of the grid connectors. The characteristic resistance value (f_{cc}) is calculated based on the arithmetic mean of the load values obtained in the push-out test (f_{cm}) and the standard deviation of these data (s), as shown in Equation 1.

$$f_{cc} = f_{cm} - 1.65 \times s \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

Next, Equations 2 and 3 are used to determine the weight of the concrete layer supported by the connectors and the required quantity of connectors, in linear meters, to support the weight of this suspended layer, respectively. It is worth noting that these equations use safety factors of 1.4 for connector resistance (γ_a) and 1.5 for the design load (γ_c).

$$P_c = c \cdot h \cdot e \cdot \rho \cdot \gamma_c \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

$$Q_m = \frac{P_c \times \gamma_a \times l}{f_{cc}} \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

Where:

- P_c - weight of the suspended concrete layer (kN);
- c - length of the suspended concrete layer (m);
- h - height of the suspended concrete layer (m);
- e - thickness of the suspended concrete layer (m);
- ρ - specific weight of reinforced concrete (kN/m³);
- γ_c - load safety factor;
- f_{cc} - characteristic strength of the connector (kN);
- l - height of the connector (m);
- γ_a - connector safety factor.

With this, the values of P_c equal to 45 kN and Q_m equal to 4.42 meters were obtained. In other words, to support the weight of the 45 kN suspended concrete layer, it is necessary to use 4.42 meters of grid connectors reinforced with curauá fiber, to be distributed along the length of the panel.

Furthermore, it is possible to determine the quantity of PerfoFRP connectors needed to support the same design load of 45 kN. The individual data from the push-out tests of the SP-12.70-1.75 group by Silva (2020) show achieved loads of 30.38 kN, 34.08 kN, 26.63 kN, and from the ESC-GN1 group by Araújo (2023), strengths of 23.66 kN, 19.86 kN, and 19.86 kN. Conducting the analysis under the same conditions, a Q_m of 0.65 meters is obtained for the PerfoFRP connectors reinforced with fiberglass from Silva (2020), and a Q_m of 0.90 meters for the PerfoFRP connectors reinforced with curauá fiber from Araújo (2023). Therefore, it is possible to use the grid connector reinforced with curauá fiber as a connection for a sandwich panel, requiring a larger quantity of connectors to compensate for the applied forces on the panel.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the objective of this study was achieved as a shear grid connector made of polymer reinforced with curauá fiber was successfully fabricated, and its load capacity (9.81 kN), displacement (12.29 mm), and rigidity (0.79 kN/mm) were determined through push-out tests.

It was found that the shear grid connectors did not achieve the same mechanical performance in terms of load capacity as the PerfoFRP connectors (SILVA, 2020; ARAUJO, 2023). However, it was demonstrated that it is possible to use the grid connectors reinforced with curauá fiber in sandwich panels. Nevertheless, it would require a substantially higher quantity of grid connectors, in linear meters, compared to the PerfoFRP connectors with which they were compared.

Greater control over the manufacturing process is important for future work since the current manual process does not allow for adjustments to the connectors after fabrication. This would ensure that the expected results align with the design values. Additionally, it would be relevant to analyze variations in the fiber-matrix ratio to evaluate which configuration would yield the best results.

Finally, it is suggested that further research investigate the thermal, hygroscopic and durability-related properties of the curauá fiber-reinforced polyester used to produce the shear connectors proposed in this paper.

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